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Simultaneous monitoring on forming pressure and residual strain of CFRP using PSFBG

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- ① **Background**
- ② Sensing principle
- ③ Forming monitoring experiment
- ④ Thermomechanical analysis
- ⑤ Conclusion

OUTLINE

1 Background

1.1 Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP)

Composite structures in aviation industry

<i>Author</i>	<i>Matrix</i>	<i>Performance</i>	<i>Forming process</i>
CFRTP	Thermoplastic	Impact resistance, recyclability, short production time	High temperature and pressure
CFRP	Thermosetting	High specific stiffness	Low temperature and pressure

* CFRTP: carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic, CFRP: carbon fiber reinforced polymer

[1] <http://www.comac.cc>

[2] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/General_Electric_GENx

[3] <https://www.plastics.gl/automotive/composites-above-the-clouds>

1 Background

1.2 Forming process

High Temperature
High Pressure

Strain/Stress
Deformation

Warpage

Warpage may lead to structural failure [4].

Forming pressure

Forming pressure affects porosity [5] and R-zone quality [6].

Porosity

R-zone quality

Out-of-plane strain that occurs during the forming process closely correlates with pressure and has a significant impact on product quality.

[4] Youssef Y, Denault J. *Polym Compos* 1998,19(3): 301.

[5] Zhang HQ, Wu Q*, Xiong K*, et al. *IEEE Sens J* 2022, 22(16): 15991.

[6] Belnoue J, Nixon-Pearson O, Thompson A. *J Eng Ind* 2018, 140(7), 071006.

1 Background

1.3 In-plane strain and temperature monitoring using FBG

Traditional electric sensor

Accuracy affected by temperature, humidity and electromagnetic interference

Fiber Bragg grating (FBG)

Small size, light weight, high temperature resistance, multiplexing capability, anti-electromagnetic interference

in-situ forming monitoring of CFRTP using FBG

<i>Author</i>	<i>Reinf/Matrix</i>	<i>Max. temp. (°C)</i>	<i>Max. pressure (MPa)</i>
Lubineau and Mulle et al. [7]	GF/PP	210	0.75
Takeda and Tsukada et al. [8]	CF/PPS	325	0.1

[7] Mulle M, Wafai H, Yudhanto A, Lubineau G*, et al. *Compos Sci Technol* 2016, 123: 143.

[8] Tsukada T*, Takeda SI, Minakuchi S, et al. *J Compos Mater* 2016, 0(0): 1-11.

1 Background

1.4 Out-of-plane strain monitoring using FBG

Low resolution

Meth: Birefringence

Obj: CFRP, Transverse strain difference

2005 Sorensen and Botsis [9]

Limited applicability

Meth: Insert trough thickness

Obj: CFRP, Out-of-plane strain

2015 Minakuchi [11]

2013 Lammens [10]

Meth: Polarization dependent loss

Obj: CFRP, Transverse strain difference

Complex demodulation

2020 Gouws [12]

Meth: Polarization-maintaining FBG

Obj: Transverse strain difference

Not applied in composite and Temperature dependent

There is a lack of a straightforward and precise multi-directional strain monitoring technique under the harsh conditions of CFRTF forming.

[9] Sorensen L, Gmür T, Botsis J*. *Compos Part A* 2006, 37(2): 270.

[10] Lammens N*, Kinet D, Chah K, Luyckx G, et al. *Compos Part A* 2013, 52: 38.

[11] Minakuchi S*. *J Compos Mater* 2015, 49(9): 1021.

[12] Gouws A*, Ford R K, Jones H B. *Eng Res Express* 2020, 2, 045016.

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2 Sensing principle

2.1 Phase-shifted fiber Bragg grating (PSFBG)

Schematic of PSFBG

Transmission spectrum

Birefringence

*FWHM: full-width at half-maximum

- PSFBG has an extremely narrow transmission peak due to phase shift.
 - Temperature and axial strain \longrightarrow wavelength shift.
 - Transverse strain \longrightarrow birefringence.

2 Sensing principle

2.2 Basic equations

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,1}}{\lambda_B} = \varepsilon_3^S - \frac{n_{eff}^2}{2} [p_{11}\varepsilon_1^S + p_{12}(\varepsilon_3^S + \varepsilon_2^S)] + \xi\Delta T, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,2}}{\lambda_B} = \varepsilon_3^S - \frac{n_{eff}^2}{2} [p_{11}\varepsilon_2^S + p_{12}(\varepsilon_3^S + \varepsilon_1^S)] + \xi\Delta T, \quad (2)$$

ε_i^S : principal strains

ΔT : temperature change

p_{11} and p_{12} : strain-optic coefficients

ξ : temperature sensitivity

Adding and subtracting Equations (1) and (2)

?

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,1} + \Delta\lambda_{B,2}}{2} = \kappa_1\varepsilon_3^S + \kappa_2(\varepsilon_1^S + \varepsilon_2^S) + \kappa_3\Delta T, \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta\lambda_{B,1} - \Delta\lambda_{B,2} = \kappa_4(\varepsilon_1^S - \varepsilon_2^S), \quad (4)$$

κ_i is constant

The derived equation indicates the correlation between spectral changes and three-directional strains.

2.3 Transfer matrix method

 $\Delta FWHM$ and peak separation vs transverse strain difference

Transmission spectrum

$\Delta\lambda_{B,A}$: average Bragg wavelength shift

$\Delta FWHM$: full-width at half-maximum

$$\Delta\lambda_{B,A} = \frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,1} + \Delta\lambda_{B,2}}{2} = \kappa_1 \varepsilon_3^S + \kappa_2 (\varepsilon_1^S + \varepsilon_2^S) + \kappa_3 \Delta T, \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta FWHM = |\Delta\lambda_{B,1} - \Delta\lambda_{B,2}| = \kappa_4 |\varepsilon_1^S - \varepsilon_2^S|. \quad (7)$$

The demodulation technique using $\Delta FWHM$ exhibits better linearity compared to peak separation.

2 Sensing principle

2.4 Interrogation method

Schematic of interrogation system

Transmission spectrum

Continuous wavelength sweep can finely characterize the narrow transmission peak of PSFBG with a resolution of 0.1 pm.

2 Sensing principle

2.5 Calibration

Temperature

Axial strain

Transverse strain

The sensitivities of temperature, axial strain, and transverse strain are calibrated before forming monitoring.

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3 Forming monitoring experiment

3.1 Sensor setup

PSFBG: phase-shifted fiber Bragg grating (FYBSENSE, 1545 nm)
EFBG: encapsulated fiber Bragg grating (SHENGHAI, 1550 nm)
SG: strain gauge (KYOWA, KFU-2-120-C1-16)

TC: thermocouple (CHINO, C060-K)
Ply 1-8: CF/PEI prepregs (TORAY, Cetex TC1000 Premium)
Al foil: aluminum foil
Steel Pad: 1 mm
Protection: steel capillary

3 Forming monitoring experiment

3.2 Forming process

Manufactured laminate

The CFRTP laminate exhibits a smooth surface and high quality.
No obvious resin rich area can be observed.

3.3 Spectra

 T_{II} : liquid-liquid transition temp. (rubbery-viscous transition temp.)

Temperature dependent modulus of PEI

III: Dwelling

ε_3^S and $|\varepsilon_1^S - \varepsilon_2^S|$ can be determined based on the wavelength shift and $\Delta FWHM$ of the transmission peak.

3 Forming monitoring experiment

3.4 Temperature monitoring

The forming temperature can be precisely monitored with an average difference of 3 °C compared to the TC.

3 Forming monitoring experiment

3.5 Axial strain monitoring

The axial residual strain can be precisely monitored with an average difference of $92 \mu\epsilon$ compared to the FBG during the cooling phase.

3.6 Transverse strain monitoring

The transverse residual strain difference can be monitored with a similar trend to the force sensor.

3 Forming monitoring experiment

3.7 Strain vs temperature

Axial strain

$T_{//} = 250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Transverse strain difference

$T_{//} = 250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Schematic of interfacial bonding

The knee points of both ε_3^S and $|\varepsilon_1^S - \varepsilon_2^S|$ occur at $T_{//}$, which can be attributed to enhanced interfacial bonding.

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5 Thermomechanical analysis

5.1 Finite element model

Material properties

Part	Material	ρ (t/mm ³)	C_p (mJ·K ⁻¹ t ⁻¹)	k (mW·mm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	E (MPa)	ν	α (K ⁻¹)
Tool	Steel	8.03×10^{-9}	5×10^8	16.3	193000	0.29	18.4×10^{-6}
Shear layer	Al	2.73×10^{-9}	9.2×10^8	19.3	70000	0.33	24×10^{-6}
CFRTP	CF/PEI	Homogenized, temperature dependent, orthotropic material properties [13]					

Mesh

Item	Value
Element	C3D20RT
Global size	1 mm
Node num	315311

5 Thermomechanical analysis

5.2 Strain distribution

The impact of CFRTP residual strain on PSFBG spectra is investigated based on the simulation results.

Strain distribution in ply 5 containing the PSFBG

In-plane strains converge to asymptotic values from edges to the center, while the out-of-plane strain exhibits a radial distribution.

5 Thermomechanical analysis

5.3 Strain comparison

Simulated strain

The axial strain of PSFBG correlates with the simulation results.

Axial strain

Transverse strain difference

The simulated in-plane strains are nearly equal:

$$\epsilon_1^H \approx \epsilon_3^H$$

The transverse strain difference shows a similar trend to the simulation but noticeable different value.

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Conclusion

01

PSFBG characteristics for CFRTP forming monitoring

Wavelength shift exhibits a cubic relation with temperature and linear relation with axial strain. FWHM exhibits a linear relation with transverse strain difference.

02

Strain transfer and decoupling

Strain relation between CFRTP and PSFBG is characterized by a strain transfer matrix, deriving the three-directional strain decoupling method.

03

Temperature and three-directional strain monitoring

Temperature shows a difference of 3 °C compared to TC. ε_3^H shows a difference of 92 $\mu\varepsilon$ compared to FBG. ε_1^H and ε_2^H show max. difference of 124 $\mu\varepsilon$ compared to simulation.

04

Forming pressure characterization

Out-of-plane strain of CFRTP exhibits higher contraction under higher forming pressure, enabling the potential for forming pressure monitoring.

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**THANK YOU
FOR LISTENING**

